

RISK FACTORS LEADING TO FOOD ALLERGY IN CHILDREN

¹Mukhamedova Nigora Saydimukhtarovna, ²Shakirova Dildora Davlyatovna

¹Associate Professor, TashPMI, ²Resident, TashPMI

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14185545>

Abstract. The article provides reasons leading to food allergies in children. Food allergies in children have not been fully studied and are currently the most pressing problem in medical practice. Food allergy is a pathological reaction caused by the ingestion of a food product, which is based on immune mechanisms. Active production of class E immunoglobulins (antibodies) in children with allergies is one of the causes of immune reactions. The manifestation of the disease occurs in children of various age groups, and more often in infants, preschool children and primary school students.

Keywords: food allergy, food allergens, immune response, young children, preschool age, non-immunological reaction, immunological reaction, breastfeeding, complementary feeding, infant formula.

Аннотация. В статье приводятся причины, приводящие к пищевой аллергии у детей. Пищевая аллергия у детей до конца не изучена и на сегодняшний день является самой актуальной проблемой медицинской практики. Пищевая аллергия - это патологическая реакция, вызванная приемом пищевого продукта, в основе которой лежат иммунные механизмы. Активная выработка иммуноглобулинов (антител) класса E у детей с аллергией, являются одной из причин иммунной реакций. Проявление заболевания встречается у детей различных возрастных групп, а чаще у младенцев, детей дошкольного возраста и у школьников начальных классов.

Ключевые слова: пищевая аллергия, пищевые аллергены, иммунная реакция, дети раннего возраста, дошкольный возраст, неиммунологическая реакция, иммунологическая реакция, естественное вскармливание, прикорм, детские молочные смеси.

Annotatsiya. Maqolada bolalarda oziq-ovqat allergiyasiga olib keladigan sabablar keltirilgan. Bolalardagi oziq-ovqat allergiyalari to'liq o'rganilmagan va hozirda tibbiy amaliyotda eng dolzarb muammo hisoblanadi. Oziq-ovqat allergiyasi - bu immunitet mexanizmlariga asoslangan oziq-ovqat mahsulotini iste'mol qilish natijasida yuzaga keladigan patologik reaksiya. Allergiyaga chalingan bolalarda E sinfidagi immunoglobulinlarni (antikorlarni) faol ishlab chiqarish immun reaksiyalarining sabablaridan biridir. Kasallikning namoyon bo'lishi turli yoshdagi bolalarda, ko'pincha chaqaloqlarda, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda va boshlang'ich maktab o'quvchilarida uchraydi.

Kalit so'zlar: oziq-ovqat allergiyalari, oziq-ovqat allergenlari immun reaksiya, chaqaloqlar, maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalar, immunologik bo'lmagan reaksiya, immunologik reaksiya tabiiy oziqlantirish, qo'shimcha oziqlantirish, chaqaloq uchu sutli yormalari.

Food allergy in children is currently the most pressing issue in medical practice. About 30% of children experience many symptoms of this disease [1]. Manifestations of the disease occur in children of various age groups, and most often in infants, preschool children and primary school students. The disease can manifest itself in a number of signs from the respiratory system, digestion, as well as skin and respiratory phenomena. The concept of food allergy means an allergic reaction that occurs after eating certain foods.

Food allergy can also be understood as "adverse reactions of the body to food products". Such reactions can be non-immunological and immunological. Non-immunological reactions or food intolerance depend on the amount of the substance in the food, are most common and are associated with a deficiency of some food enzymes (for example, lactose deficiency), the toxic effect of some substances in food products or their microbial contamination. Immunological reactions or food allergies do not depend on the dose of the antigen, these reactions are associated with an incorrect reaction of the child's immune system.

According to the World Health Organization, the frequency of food allergies varies, on average, manifestations of food allergies occur in 2.5% of the population [3]. At the same time, of course, the problem is most relevant in infancy and early childhood [1]. Symptoms of food allergies in the anamnesis are noted in 17.3% of children [4]. However, the prevalence of proven food allergies in developed countries among young children is 6-8%, in adolescence - 2-4% and in adults - 2%. Among children suffering from atopic dermatitis, the frequency of food allergies exceeds 30% [2,5,7].

Food allergies in young children are caused by some components of food products, and especially 6 products provoke adverse reactions: cow's milk, soy, eggs, nuts, peanuts, wheat. Sometimes the pathology can manifest itself as a cross-reaction, intolerance to pollen or chemical irritants can cause food allergies. For the reaction to occur, in addition to the presence of an allergen, the child must also have predisposing factors. These include the following factors:

- genetic predisposition;
- pathologies, which is suffered by the baby during intrauterine development, as well as diseases of the mother transmitted to the child through the placental barrier during childbirth;
- the child's susceptibility to frequent infectious diseases;
- artificial feeding;
- poor environmental conditions in the region of residence;
- the desire of parents to create “sterile conditions” for the child to live in;
- introducing complementary foods to infants before 6 months;
- various functional disorders in the digestive system.

Heredity and genetics play a major role in the development of food allergies in children. 30-50% of children develop allergic diseases if one of the parents has an allergy, 60-80% if both parents have an allergy, and 12% of children in families where there was no allergy.

The causes of impaired immune maturation in young children may be exposure to strong allergens, environmental pollution, frequent infectious diseases, the use of antibiotics (they destroy the intestinal microflora that is involved in immune maturation), and etc.

Most often, parents' mistakes in organizing the nutrition of young children become one of the factors of food allergies. These include:

- large portion size of food; introduction of several new foods at the same time;
- feed babies with foods that are not suitable for the child's age, citrus fruits, chocolate and other allergens.

The risk of developing allergies also increases if a woman smoked during pregnancy and the fetus experienced oxygen starvation.

The direct cause of an allergic reaction is also contact of a predisposed organism with an allergen. Allergens can enter the body in several ways: oral - by swallowing; respiratory - through the respiratory tract; contact - when in contact with the skin.

Thus, it is important to carry out primary prevention of the disease in a timely manner. At the current level of development of science and technology, we have no opportunity to change genetic predisposition, the strategy of primary prevention of allergies is oriented towards the impact of factors and is focused on early age, since it is at this time that the immune system is formed and at the same time the primary contact with proteins that trigger the allergic pathogenetic process occurs. Preventive measures are: long-term continuation of natural feeding; refusal to use baby food mixtures; correct introduction of complementary foods to infants; refusal to consume products containing preservatives and dyes. Knowing the factors leading to food allergies, it is possible to prevent and carry out prevention of food allergies in children.

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